

Exploring the cognitive effects of hearing loss in adult rats: Implications for visuospatial attention, social behavior, and prefrontal neural activity

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ABSTRACT

Age-related hearing loss in humans has been associated with cognitive decline, though the underlying mechanisms remain unknown. We investigated the long-term effects of hearing loss on attention, impulse control, social interaction, and neural activity within medial prefrontal cortex (mPFC) subregions.

Hearing loss was induced in adult rats via intracochlear neomycin injection ($n = 13$), with non-operated rats as controls ($n = 10$). Rats were tested for motor activity (open field), coordination (Rotarod), and social interaction (including ultrasonic vocalization, USV) before surgery and at weeks 1, 2, 4, 8, 16, and 24 post-surgery. From week 8 on, rats were trained in the five-choice serial reaction time task (5-CSRTT) to assess visuospatial attention and impulse control. Finally, oscillatory neuronal activity in mPFC subregions was recorded with multielectrode arrays during anesthesia, followed by immunohistological staining for NeuN⁺ and Parvalbumin⁺ cells.

Deafened rats were more active than controls, whereas social interaction and USV were temporarily reduced. They also had difficulties to learn the concept of the 5-CSRTT paradigm and made more incorrect responses. Electrophysiology showed decreased power in theta, alpha, and beta frequency, and enhanced high gamma band in the mPFC in deafened rats, which was most pronounced in the cingulate subregion (Cg1). The number of NeuN⁺ and Parvalbumin⁺ cells, however, did not differ between groups.

The behavioral deficits together with the altered neuronal activity found in the Cg1 subregion of the mPFC in adult deafened rats may be used as an endophenotype to elucidate the mechanisms behind the cognitive decline seen in older patients with hearing loss.

Introduction

Hearing loss is recognized for its many effects on human health. Its consequences span all age groups, manifesting as hyperactivity and socioemotional difficulties in children (Lieu et al., 2020) while showing a compelling association with dementia in the elderly (Kral et al., 2016; Lin et al., 2013; Livingston et al., 2020). Moreover, untreated hearing loss in adults is often accompanied by reduced social communication, which additionally contributes to cognitive decline (Lin & Albert, 2014; Maharani et al., 2019). The complex relationship between hearing and cognitive function is highlighted by the dependence of speech recognition outcomes and cognitive ability in cochlear implant recipients

(Akeroyd, 2008; Lazard et al., 2012; Naples et al., 2021).

Previous studies mainly focused on the effects of hearing loss on auditory function and neural plasticity along the auditory pathway (Cardon et al., 2012; Nadhimi & Llano, 2021; Wingfield & Peelle, 2015). Understanding the impact of hearing loss on executive functions and neuroplasticity in higher order cognitive brain regions, however, remains an ongoing challenge (Ball et al., 2011; Galloway et al., 2008; Kronenberger et al., 2013, 2014; Marschark et al., 2017). A recent neuroimaging study in humans with long-term hearing loss revealed enhanced coupling between auditory areas and the dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (PFC), a central region for higher cognitive function (Luan et al., 2019). Substantial evidence, that hearing loss is a potential

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precursor for cognitive decline, would strongly support early hearing loss treatment as a preventive measure (Kim et al., 2021; Mammo et al., 2018; Mosnier et al., 2018; Naples et al., 2021; Powell et al., 2021).

Animal models are useful in this context, as they allow for the exploration of hearing loss in a controlled setting (Ghafarimoghdam et al., 2022). In a previous study, we tested the impact of hearing loss in adult rats on spatial learning and neuronal activity in the medial prefrontal cortex (mPFC; Johne et al., 2022). Although the effects on learning and memory in a spatial radial maze paradigm were only minor and transient, altered neuronal activities in the mPFC indicated effects of hearing loss on neuronal networks with potential consequences for cognitive function not addressed in that study (Johne et al., 2022).

The 5-choice serial reaction time task (5-CSRTT) has been developed as an analogue of the continuous performance test in humans to assess visuospatial attention and impulsivity of rodents in a specially adapted operant chamber (Robbins, 2002). This task has been widely used to better understand the functional diversity of the mPFC in rats with respect to executive cognitive processes, including attention and impulse control (Dalley et al., 2004, 2008). There is broad consensus that the mPFC consists of three anatomically and functionally distinct subregions: the cingulate cortex (Cg1), the prelimbic cortex (PL) and the infralimbic cortex (IL). In addition, the secondary motor cortex (M2) is discussed as another subregion of the mPFC, although this region also serves motor functions (Brecht et al., 2004; Erlich et al., 2011; Hockley & Malmierca, 2024; Laubach et al., 2018; Yoshida et al., 2009). Experiments using the 5-CSRTT have predominantly indicated a role of the Cg1 in attentional aspects of performance, whereas the PL and infralimbic subregions play a role in inhibitory response control (Fisher et al., 2005). To further study the effect of hearing loss on cognition, we investigated attention related behavior in an adult rat model of deafness. Hearing loss was induced by intracochlear injection of ototoxic Neomycin. Eight weeks after surgery behavioral testing for attention and impulse control started by training rats in the 5-CSRTT, where rats had to respond to a brief, unpredictable visual stimulus presented in one of five locations. Also, ultrasonic communication during social interaction, and motor activity were tested over a period of six months. Finally, we investigated the influence of hearing loss on neuronal activity in the mPFC via a 32-channel electrode placed across M2, Cg1 and PL subregions. As Parvalbumin (PV⁺) interneurons in the mPFC control the timing of pyramidal cell output, thereby contributing to disturbances of oscillatory network synchrony associated with cognitive deficits (Miyamae et al., 2017; Sohal et al., 2009), the mPFC was finally processed for immunohistological staining of neuronal nuclei antigen (NeuN) and PV⁺ interneurons.

Material und methods

Animals

Adult male Sprague-Dawley rats (<225 g at start of experiments, purchased from Charles River Laboratories, Sulzfeld, Germany; n = 23) were housed in groups of two to four animals per Makrolon Type IV open cage under controlled environmental conditions (22 ± 2 °C; 55 ± 10 % humidity; 10/14 h dark/light cycle with lights on at 06:00 a.m.). Tap water was freely available and 14–16 g of standard rodent chow (Altromin, Lage, Germany) was fed per day and animal to enhance saliency of reward pellets during behavioral testing while ensuring weekly weight gain until about 450 g at the final experiments. Body weight and clinical scores were assessed at least twice a week to ensure the well-being of the rats. All experiments comply with the ARRIVE guidelines, were carried out in accordance with the EU directive 2010/63/ EU for animal experiments and were approved by the local animal ethics committee (Lower Saxony State Office for Consumer Protection and Food Safety, AZ 18/2874). All efforts were made to minimize the number of animals and their suffering.

Study design

Animals were randomly assigned into two experimental groups: (1) the deafened group (n = 13), in which hearing loss was induced via intracochlear injection of Neomycin and (2) the non-operated group (n = 10) for control. Auditory brainstem response (ABR) measurements were conducted in all rats before surgery to ensure normal hearing, respectively hearing loss after surgery in the deafened group.

Open field, Rotarod, and social interaction were tested the week before surgery (week 0) and in weeks 1, 2, 4, 8, 16, and 24 after surgery. Beginning at week 8, rats were additionally tested for social preference and trained in the 5-CSRTT. After behavioral testing at week 24, electrophysiological recordings were performed in the Cg1 and PL subregions of the mPFC and the M2 in a final setting during urethane anesthesia. Thereafter, all brains were prepared for immunohistological analysis of PV⁺ and NeuN⁺ cells in the mPFC. A summary of the experimental design is shown in Fig. 1A.

The software SigmaStat 4.0 (Systat Software Inc., San Jose, CA, USA) was used for all statistical analyses. All tests were applied two-sided and a p < 0.05 considered significant. The graphs were created with GraphPad Prism 9 (GraphPad Software, LLC Version 9.3.1; Boston, USA). More details are given in the different subsections about experiments.

Surgery for deafening

As recently described (Jelinek et al., 2024; Johne et al., 2022), deafening surgery was performed by injecting Neomycin into the round window of the inner ear under general chloral hydrate anesthesia (360 mg/kg, i.p.). Analgesia regime comprised local anesthesia (Xylocain, 1 %; AstraZeneca, Wilmington, USA) applied to the postauricular region and systemic injection of Carprofen (5 mg/kg, s.c.; RIMADYL®, Zoetis, Germany). A skin incision was made in the postauricular region, the trapezius muscle dissected and the facial nerve identified directly over the bulla. A slow speed 0.5 mm diameter rose burr was used to drill a small hole into the bulla. Subsequently 3x5 µl Neomycin (5 mg dissolved in 1 ml phosphate-buffered saline (PBS), adjusted to pH 7.4) was injected through the round window into the cochlea with a 30-gauge micro Hamilton syringe. The skin was sutured and the procedure repeated on the opposite side. Animals received systemic analgesia for two more days after surgery (2.5 mg/kg Carprofen s.c.). Non-operated control animals did not undergo any surgery or medication.

Hearing loss assessment

Click-evoked ABR was performed to evaluate deafening surgery, as described in Johne et al. (2022). Subdermal monopolar needle electrodes were positioned at the vertex of the skull behind the left or right ear, and in the neck as a grounding electrode to obtain ABRs. Stimuli were generated using an Audiology Lab system. The acquisition system (Otoconsult Comp., Frankfurt, Germany) running on a PC was connected to an AD converter (National Instruments NI-USB-6251, Austin, TX, USA) and an analog USB-controlled attenuator (PNS1, Otoconsult Comp., Frankfurt, Germany) coupled to a calibrated DT48 speaker (Beyerdynamic, Heilbronn, Germany) positioned close to the ear. Condensation clicks of 50 µs duration were presented at levels from 10 to 100 dB SPL p.e. in 10 dB steps. After intracochlear injection of Neomycin rats were tested for ABR up to 120 dB SPL to ensure complete hearing loss. The clicks were repeated 200 times per volume with an inter-stimulus interval of 113 ms. For analysis, 200 sweeps per volume were averaged using custom code in MATLAB (The MathWorks, Natick, USA). The signals were digitally filtered (300–3000 Hz). Presence of ABRs was determined manually by detection of a spike 2–3 ms after stimulus (Schopf et al., 2014; Tillein et al., 2012). ABR thresholds were compared between deafened and control rats with Student's *t*-test.

A) Experimental design

B1) ABR hearing threshold

B2) Representative examples of ABRs

Fig. 1. (A) Timeline and Auditory Brainstem Response (ABR) measures. Experimental design. (B1) Effects of the deafening surgery to the auditory brainstem response of non-operated, and deafened rats with data shown as boxplots with whiskers from 10 to 90 percentile pre- and post-surgery. (B2) Representative examples of ABRs before and after surgery are shown in dB SPL.

Testing for motor behavior and social interaction

Motor behavior

Open field: Locomotive behavior was tested in an open field arena (60x60x30 cm). Rats were placed in the open field arena for ten minutes. The locomotor distance was automatically evaluated using video recordings from above the arena (TopScan; TopView Analyzing System 2.0; Clever Sys Inc., Reston, USA).

Rotarod: Motor coordination was tested by placing the animals on a Rotarod inside a test chamber (10,5x43x43 cm; Rotarod, series 8, IITC Life Science, Cambridge, UK), which rotated with accelerating speed for 60 s (starting speed: five rotations per minute; top speed: 15 rotations per minute) followed by another 60 s with constant speed (15 rotations per minute). Rats were tested on three consecutive trials. Time was

taken for the rat to descend the rotating rod. For analysis, the maximum time spent on the Rotarod was used.

Social interaction and ultrasonic vocalization

For experimental assessment of social interaction, two cage mates were placed in an open field arena for ten minutes. The interactions were video-recorded via a camera installed above the test arena and evaluated using the ODlog Software (Macropod Software™ version 2.7.2) and the frequency of total social interactions comprising anogenital and frontal sniffing, following, and play-fighting assessed.

During social interaction, also the rat’s ultrasonic vocalization (USV) was recorded using the Avisoft ultrasound recorder, which was connected to the Avisoft SAS Lab Pro software (Avisoft Bioacustics, Glienicke, Germany). The following types of USV in the spectrum of 50 to 60

Fig. 2. Assessment of Locomotor Activity. The graph shows (A) the total distance and (B) time on Rotarod for deafened and non-operated groups at the different weeks (mean \pm SEM). Significant differences between groups are indicated by Asterisks (*), significant differences within groups compared to week 0 as circle (o), two-way RM ANOVA with post-hoc Bonferroni pairwise comparison, $p < 0.05$.

Hz were differentiated: flat, trill, step, and mixed, as well as overlap (OLP) in case of simultaneous vocalizations of the two rats (see Fig. 3B1). For analysis, the total number of vocalizations during social interaction as well as of the different types of vocalizations in weeks 4 and 16 were used. In addition, the USV per social interactions was analyzed.

Statistical analysis of motor behavior and social interaction

For statistical analysis of open field, Rotarod and social interaction a two-way repeated measure (RM) analysis of variance (ANOVA) was applied with factors group (deafened or non-operated) and weeks (week 0 pre-surgery, and weeks 1, 2, 4, 8, 16, and 24 post-surgery), followed by a post-hoc Bonferroni *t*-test for multiple comparisons in case of significance. Additionally, the number of different types of USV, and the ratio of USV per social interaction was compared between groups at weeks 4 and 16 by using a *t*-test. All tests were applied two-sided and a $p < 0.05$ considered significant.

Five-choices serial reaction time task

For testing, a 9-hole box (Campden Instruments Ltd., Loughborough, UK) with corresponding software ABET 2 Standard (Version 22.03.22.0; Sagamore Pkwy N, Lafayette, United States) was used. In this box, every second of the nine holes located on the back panel was covered, leaving holes 1, 3, 5, 7, and 9 open. The food-tray for rewarding with pellets (Dustless Precision Pellets 45 mg, Rodent Purified Diet BioServ, Flemington, United States) was located on the front panel.

Training started 8 weeks after surgery with a habituation phase of 30 min for two days. On the first day, the rat was placed into the box with the house light on and the food tray filled with rewarding pellets with a concealing flap fixed in an open position. On the second day, the rats had to push the flap to get access to the pellets in the food tray. The five holes on the back panel were equipped with one pellet in each hole. For training, the rat was placed in the box and had to detect a flashlight popping up pseudo randomly in one of the five holes. All training levels comprised a maximum schedule time of 30 min or 100 trials, whichever came first. The first trial was initiated by a free pellet followed by an inter-trial interval (ITI) of 5 s. Thereafter, the rat had to react with a nose-poke into a hole that was illuminated; in the first level for a 60 s light stimulus duration. A correct response within a hold value of 60 s was rewarded with a pellet in the food tray that was illuminated with light. Upon pushing the flap of the food tray to get the reward pellet the

next trial was initiated. If the rat poked into a wrong (non-illuminated) hole, ignored the stimulus, or poked during the ITI of 5 s or more than once, a time-out period of darkness lasting 5 s followed.

The rat had to achieve an accuracy of more than 80 % and an omission rate less than 20 % in one schedule to qualify for the next training level. During the next training levels the light stimulus duration and the limited hold value gradually decreased (see schedule in Fig. 4B) to the desired stimulus duration of 1 s and a limited hold value of 5 s in the final level 8. Whenever rats had learning difficulties (more than 20 days without achieving an accuracy greater than 80 % and an omission rate less than 20 %), the rat was placed back two levels below the actual level. With this paradigm, the total number of training days per difficult level, the means of incorrect responses, the premature responses as well as the reward latency per level were calculated.

For statistical analysis of the training days, the incorrect responses, the premature responses as well as the reward latencies per level during training in the 5-CSRTT a two-way RM ANOVA with factor group (deafened or non-operated) and factor level (1–8) was applied, followed by a post-hoc Bonferroni *t*-test for multiple comparisons in case of significance. All tests were applied two-sided and a $p < 0.05$ considered significant.

Electrophysiology recordings

For electrophysiological recordings a single shank 32-channel electrode (Neuronexus Technologies, Ann Arbor, MI, USA) was used, which is optimal for recording of oscillatory local field potentials (LFPs). Rats were anesthetized with urethane (1.5 g/kg; ethyl carbamate, Sigma–Aldrich, injected i.p. with additional 20 % doses as needed). The adequate depth of anaesthesia was checked by foot pinch. The incision site was infiltrated with a local anesthetic, Xylocain (1 % AstraZeneca, Wilmington, DE). Ophthalmic ointment (Bepanthen, Bayer, Germany) was applied to the eyes to avoid corneal dehydration. Rats were placed in a stereotaxic frame and body temperature was maintained at 37 ± 0.5 °C by a heating device (FHC, Bowdoinham, ME). A small craniotomy was made over the target coordinates over the mPFC (relative to Bregma): anterior-posterior (AP) + 2.7 mm; mediolateral (ML) –0.8 mm. Thereafter, the multichannel electrode (1x32 channels; electrode diameter: 15 μ m; 100 μ m interelectrode distance, contact size of 177 μ m²) was inserted with the electrode tip at 4.5 mm ventral from dura. Thus, the electrode shank was placed across M2 and the Cg1 and PL subregions of the mPFC. Before insertion, the electrode was coated with

A) Social Interaction

B1) Examples for Ultrasonic Vocalization

Week 4

Week 16

B2) Number of USV

B3) Number of USV

B4) USV/ social interaction

B5) USV/ social interaction

Fig. 3. Social Interaction and ultrasonic vocalization. (A) Total number of social interaction with data shown as means \pm SEM. Significant differences between groups are indicated by Asterisks (*), and significant differences within groups compared to week 0 as circle ($^{\circ}$, two-way RM ANOVA with post-hoc Bonferroni pairwise comparison, $p < 0.05$). (B1) USVs, representative examples shown as sonograms, were differentiated into the following structures: flat, trill, step, and mixed, as well as overlap (OLP) in case of simultaneous vocalization between the rats. Number of USVs in total and differentiated in the structures at (B2) week 4 and (B3) week 16 post-surgery. Ratio of USVs per social interaction in (B4) week 4 and (B5) week 16. Data are shown as boxplots with whiskers from 10 to 90 percentile. Significant differences between groups are indicated by asterisks (*, students t -test, $p < 0.05$).

fluorescence DiI (Sigma-Aldrich Chemie, Steinheim, Germany) to allow allocation of the channels to the mPFC subregions after histological processing. The electrode signal was amplified ($8000 \times$), passed through a headstage and acquired through a multichannel recording system (Lynx-8 amplifier system, butterworth filter: 1 Hz–9 kHz, rolloff: 12 dB per octave, Neuralynx, Bozeman, MT, USA) and stored through a custom-built recording setup and the corresponding stimulation and data acquisition software (AudiologyLab, Otoconsult, Frankfurt,

Germany) at a sampling rate of 25 kHz using a 32-channel MIO card (NI-6259 National Instruments, Austin, USA) as previously described by Foremny et al (2021).

The raw LFP signals were band-pass filtered from 0.5 to 100 Hz and downsampled to 1000 Hz. Epochs of 600 s without major artifacts were used for the frequency analysis of LFP activity in the M2, Cg1, and PL. The power spectrum of the LFPs were estimated using Welch's method. We used the pwelch function of MATLAB (MathWorks, Inc., version

A) Schematic Setting

B) Training Schedule

Level	Stimulus Duration (sec)	Limited Hold Value (sec)
1	60	60
2	30	30
3	20	20
4	10	10
5	5	5
6	2.5	5
7	1.5	5
8	1	5

C) Training Days

D) Incorrect Responses

E) Premature Responses

F) Reward Latency

Fig. 4. 5-CSRTT. (A) Schematic drawing of the 5-CSRTT. (B) Training schedule. Parameters were gradually reduced to the desired stimulus duration of 0.5 s and a limited hold value of 5 s. (C) Total training days per level, (D) incorrect and (E) premature responses as well as reward latency with data shown as boxplots with whiskers from 10 to 90 percentile. Differences between deafened and non-operated rats are indicated by an asterisks (*, ANOVA with post-hoc Bonferroni pairwise comparison, $p < 0.05$).

2023a) with blocks of 4096 samples for the discrete Fourier transformation which resulted in a frequency resolution of 0.24 Hz. We utilized a 4 s window length with 80 % overlap to maintain consistency across our spectral analyses. A Hamming window function was applied

to mitigate the spectral leakage phenomenon. For comparison of power at different frequency bands, the area under the computed power density spectrum in specified frequency ranges was calculated and averaged for six contacts allocated to the different mPFC subregions. Comparative

analysis comprised the following frequency bands: theta (4–8 Hz), alpha (8–12 Hz), beta (12–30 Hz), low gamma (30–45 Hz), and high gamma (55–100 Hz).

To analyze the complexity of LFPs signals the Higuchi dimension (Higuchi, 1988) was computed from the spontaneous LFP activity using Matlab. The Higuchi dimension has been previously used to analyze changes in EEG signals in Alzheimer's and Parkinson's disease (Accardo et al., 1997; Averna et al., 2023; Smits et al., 2016). We choose a value of $k_{\max} = 40$. Higuchi's algorithm is applied to a time series $X : \{1, \dots, N\} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ as follows. For each $1 \leq k \leq k_{\max}$ and each $1 \leq m \leq k$ define

$$L_m(k) = \frac{N-1}{\left[\frac{N-m}{k}\right] k^2} \sum_{i=1}^{\left[\frac{N-m}{k}\right]} |X(m+ik) - X(m+(i-1)k)|.$$

For $1 \leq k \leq k_{\max}$ let

$$L(k) = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{m=1}^k L_m(k)$$

The Higuchi dimension of X is defined to be the slope D of the best fitting linear curve through the points $\left(\log \frac{1}{k}, \log L(k)\right)$, $1 \leq k \leq k_{\max}$, determined using a simple linear regression. The Higuchi dimension is between 1 and 2, a higher value corresponding to higher signal complexity. Comparison of Higuchi dimension and band power between the deafened and non-operated groups was performed using the Mann-Whitney U test as the data was not normally distributed.

Immunohistochemistry for NeuN and Parvalbumin

For histological analysis, rats were deeply anesthetized at the end of experiments and underwent transcardial perfusion with 0.1 M PBS followed by 4 % paraformaldehyde. Brains were removed and postfixed in 4 % paraformaldehyde for at least 24 h. Thereafter, brains were transferred to 30 % sucrose solution and cut in 40 μm coronal sections using a cryomicrotome (Leica Microsystems, Wetzlar, Germany). Sections on slides were washed with PBS (BIO&SELL GmbH, Nürnberg, Germany) and blocked for 1 h with 5 % normal goat serum, 0.5 % Triton X-100 and 2 % BSA in PBS (AppliChem GmbH Darmstadt, Germany); PanReac Quimica SLU (Barcelona, Spain); Sigma-Aldrich Chemie (St. Louis, USA), respectively). The primary antibodies were incubated for one hour at room temperature and overnight at 4° (PV (1:500; PaV Rabbit; Sigma-Aldrich Chemie, Steinheim, Germany), NeuN (1:400; Chemicon, Temecula, USA)). The secondary antibodies Alexa 488 (1:300; Invitrogen by Thermo Fisher Scientific; Life Technologies Corporation, Eugene, USA) and Alexa 568 (1:200; Invitrogen by Thermo Fisher Scientific; Life Technologies Corporation, Eugene, USA) were incubated for 1 h. True Black (1:40; 40x in DMSO; BIOTIUM, Fremont, USA), was incubated for 10 min. Slides were mounted with Slow Fade Gold Mounting medium with DAPI (Invitrogen Molecular Probes, Eugene, USA).

All slices were examined with a Leica TCS SP8 fluorescence microscope (Leica Microsystems, Bensheim, Germany) and analyzed using the ImageJ software (Bethesda, MD, USA). Furthermore, the images for quantification were blinded to mitigate potential observer's bias. The density of NeuN⁺ and PV⁺ cells was determined by calculating their number per mm² within the mPFC using both hemispheres of one slice per animal at 2.70 mm anterior of bregma). The mean number of NeuN⁺ and PV⁺ cells of both hemispheres was used for statistical analysis with the Mann-Whitney U test.

Results

Clinical Outcome

Two animals were excluded from the deafened group due to incomplete hearing loss, i.e., ABR measurements less than 90 dB SPL on both sides. This resulted in a group size of $n = 11$ for the deafened group and $n = 10$ for the non-operated group. All rats recovered from surgery with no substantial clinical disturbances despite mild trunk postural impairment in three rats in the direct postoperative state. As these mild motor impairments ceased within the first six days after surgery, all data of these rats were used for statistical analysis.

Auditory brainstem response measurement

All rats showed normal hearing before surgery (40–50 dB SPL). The click ABR thresholds before surgery did not differ between rats assigned to the deafened group or the non-operated controls. After intracochlear injection of Neomycin, the ABR of the deafened group was significantly enhanced to more than 90 dB SPL, both compared to the preoperative ABR measures and to that of non-operated controls (significant interaction between factors group x time shown by two-way RM ANOVA: $F_{2;50} = 222.553p < 0.001$, followed by post-hoc pairwise comparison with Bonferroni test; Fig. 1B1). Representative examples of ABR measurements before and after surgery are shown in Fig. 1B2.

Motor behavior

Open field: Before deafening surgery, the distance covered in the open field as measure for locomotor activity did not differ between groups. Deafening led to enhanced locomotor activity during the whole testing period, both compared to the preoperative measure and compared to the distance covered by the non-operated group which did not change during testing at weeks 1–24 (significant interaction of factors group and weeks shown by two-way RM ANOVA: $F_{6;113} = 2.722$, $p = 0.017$, followed by post-hoc pairwise comparison with Bonferroni test; Fig. 2A).

Rotarod: Before surgery, the time on the Rotarod as measure for motor coordination and balance did not differ between groups. While the time on the Rotarod did not change in the deafened group in the observation period, the time on the Rotarod of rats of the non-operated group increased from the 2nd postoperative week on, both compared to the preoperative measure and compared to the non-operated group (significant interaction of factors group and weeks shown by two-way RM ANOVA: $F_{6;113} = 4.830$, $p < 0.001$, followed by post-hoc pairwise comparison with Bonferroni test; Fig. 2B).

Social interaction and ultrasonic vocalization

Only the number of anogenital and frontal sniffing, and following was included in the total number of social interactions as the adult rats used in this study did not show play-fighting. Before surgery, the interaction with a social partner did not differ between groups. While the social interaction in the non-operated group did not change during the observation period of postoperative weeks 1–24, deafened rats interacted less in weeks 1, 4, 8, and 24 after surgery compared to the preoperative measure, and also less than the non-operated group in weeks 4 and 8 (significant interaction of factors group and weeks shown by two-way RM ANOVA: $F_{6;114} = 3.061$; $p < 0.01$, followed by post-hoc pairwise comparison with Bonferroni test; Fig. 3A).

In both groups, USV of the flat, trill, step, mixed and overlap type were observed in the frequency range of 50 to 60 Hz (typical examples are shown in Fig. 3B1). In week 4, the deafened group vocalized less in total, which is mainly due to less vocalization of the mixed type in deafened rats (t -test $p < 0.004$). In week 16 after surgery, however, vocalization of groups did not differ (t -test $p > 0.7$). Analysis of USV

Fig. 5. Local Field Potentials and Power Spectrum. (A) Schematic drawing of the analyzed brain region with the position of the electrode from the atlas of Paxinos and Watson (1986). (B) Example action potential waveforms are shown for each of the electrode's 32-channels along with an explanation of the channel assignment to the respective regions M2, Cg1, and PL. Absolute power of theta, alpha, beta, low gamma and high gamma band activity in the (C) M2, (D) Cg1, and (E) PL. (F) Higuchi dimension. Data are shown as boxplots with whiskers from 10 to 90 percentile. Significant differences between deafened and non-operated rats are shown as asterisks (*, Mann-Whitney *U* test, $p < 0.05$). Trends are shown as asterisks in brackets ((*), Mann-Whitney *U* test, $p < 0.1$). Power spectral density of (G) M2, (H) Cg1, and (I) PL. Abbreviations: M2 motor cortex; Cg1 cingulate cortex; PL prelimbic cortex.

Fig. 6. Immunohistochemistry. (A) The analyzed brain region mPFC is depicted on schematic drawing of coronal sections from the atlas of Paxinos & Watson (1998). (B) The blue rectangle indicates the analyzed area. NeuN-staining. Representative photomicrographs and corresponding quantitative analysis of NeuN-positive cells. (C) Parvalbumin-staining. Representative photomicrographs and corresponding quantitative analysis of parvalbumin-positive cells. Data are shown as boxplots with whiskers from 10 to 90 percentile.

during social interactions showed that deafened rats exhibited fewer USV per social interaction than non-operated counterparts in week 4 (t -test $p = 0.006$) but not in week 16 post-surgery (t -test $p = 0.704$; Fig. 3B2-5).

Five-choices serial reaction time task

All rats learned the 5-CSRTT with an accuracy over 80 % and an omission rate under 20 % in last level of the training schedule (level 8). However, the deafened group needed significantly more days in the first level than the non-operated group, indicating difficulties to understand the concept of the paradigm, whereas training days for all subsequent levels did not differ between groups (i.e., level 2–8; significant interaction of factors group and levels shown by two-way RM ANOVA: $F_{8,142} = 2.557$, $p = 0.012$, followed by post-hoc pairwise comparison with Bonferroni test; Fig. 4C). In addition, the deafened group made more incorrect responses across all levels (significant effect for the factor group shown by two-way RM ANOVA: $F_{1,126} = 8.129$, $p = 0.011$; Fig. 4D). However, the premature responses and the reward latency did not differ between groups in all levels (Fig. 4E-F).

Electrophysiology

Histological analysis verified that the 32 shank electrode was placed across the M2, Cg1 and PL subregions of the mPFC, thus allowing to allocate six of the 32 channels to each of the different subregions (see Fig. 5A-B). Analysis of the average LFP activity of the six contacts for each subregion showed that the absolute power of the theta, alpha, and beta frequency band was lower in the Cg1 of the deafened group than in

controls ($p < 0.05$). In the PL, however, only beta band activity was significantly reduced in deafened rats ($p < 0.05$) while theta and alpha did not reach the level of significance (p between 0.1 and 0.05). In the Cg1 subregion, only high gamma activity was increased in the deafened group ($p < 0.05$, Fig. 5), while low gamma activity was not affected by deafening. No significant differences were observed in the power of the different frequency bands in the spectral analysis for the M2 area.

Further, analysis of the Higuchi dimension revealed only a trend for enhanced complexity in the Cg1 region between non-operated and deafened rats ($p < 0.05$, Fig. 5F).

Immunohistochemistry for NeuN and Parvalbumin

All 11 deafened rats and 8 non-operated controls were used for statistical analysis, as due to poor perfusion and technical issues, two rats of the non-operated control group were excluded. Representative photomicrographs of immunostained brain slices of rats at week 24 after surgery are shown in Fig. 6B. Statistical analysis of the number of NeuN⁺ or PV⁺ cells in the mPFC did not show any significant differences between the deafened and the non-operated control group (Fig. 6C).

Discussion

The effects of hearing loss have primarily been studied in terms of auditory function and neural plasticity throughout the auditory pathway (Cardon et al., 2012; Wingfield & Peelle, 2015). Nevertheless, in frontal cortical areas altered neural activity has been described in challenging listening conditions and as a compensatory mechanism for deficits in speech processing in adults with age-related hearing loss (Binder et al.,

2004; Du et al., 2016; Zekveld et al., 2006). The potential impact of hearing loss on non-auditory behavioral function and neural plasticity in frontal cortical areas, however, has only recently received attention (Johne et al., 2022; Rosemann & Thiel, 2020).

Using Neomycin-induced deafening in adult rats, we previously reported rather small and transient behavioral deficits in a radial arm maze task for learning and memory, on social interaction and on motor activity. Yet, in the mPFC, a central region associated with higher cognitive function, neural activity of deafened rats differed from that of controls, suggesting effects on neural networks outside the central auditory system with potential consequences for cognitive function that were not tested in the previous study (Johne et al., 2022). We therefore investigated the effect of hearing loss on the mPFC more closely, both in terms of mPFC-related behaviors such as learning, attention and impulsivity, and in terms of neural plasticity in its subregions.

The rat mPFC is a functionally heterogeneous region composed of the Cg1, the PL and IL, which are defined by different inputs and projection patterns, making them anatomically and functionally distinct (Gabbott et al., 1997; Laubach et al., 2018; Vogt & Paxinos, 2014). Based on connections with the mediodorsal nucleus of the thalamus (MD) it has been suggested that the mPFC has functions similar to those of the primate dorsolateral PFC. Recent studies, however, have challenged this view (Laubach et al., 2018). The MD also project to the M2, which has therefore also been considered as part of the rodent prefrontal cortex, although this region has projections to jaw and tongue muscles (Yoshida et al., 2009) and electric stimulation produces movements of head and neck muscles (Brecht et al., 2004; Erlich et al., 2011). Nevertheless, although not an auditory brain area according to the classical definition, the auditory pathway, including the auditory cortex, primarily targets the Cg1 subregion of the mPFC (Åhrlund-Richter et al., 2019; Hockley & Malmierca, 2024; Sun et al., 2022). This is consistent with the observation that from Cg1-PL-IL there is a shift from primarily sensory inputs to more limbic inputs (Hoover & Vertes, 2007), suggesting that auditory cortex inputs are likely concentrated to the Cg1. Notably, the Cg1 area is a hub of cognitive and emotional control, and it is highly preserved across mammals (Burgos-Robles et al., 2019). Interestingly, it is activated when humans observe the facial expressions (e.g., Simon et al., 2006; Vrticka et al., 2009) and vocalizations of others (e.g., Johnstone et al., 2006).

In line with this concept, analysis of electrophysiological recordings in the Cg1 of deafened rats showed reduced absolute power in the alpha, theta, and beta frequency ranges together with increased activity in the high gamma frequency range. These changes were less pronounced in the more ventral PL subregion of the mPFC, and absent in the secondary motor area M2. Studies in humans have postulated that a decrease in theta and alpha band activity during encoding appears to be associated with increased task difficulty and impaired cognitive mapping (Lasaponara et al., 2019; Lithfous et al., 2015; Puma et al., 2018; Trammell et al., 2017). Our previous studies of hearing loss in adulthood rats have shown a coincidence with the development of decreased theta and increased gamma frequency LFPs synchronizations in mPFC networks (i.e., coherency of mPFC and inferior colliculus; Johnne et al., 2022). Furthermore, we demonstrated a general trend towards increased Higuchi FD levels in all mPFC subregions, although the increase was only significant in the Cg1 area of the deafened rats. With that regard, the FD is increasingly recognized for its sensitivity to neuronal network alterations associated with various neurological disorders and has been used to analyze changes in EEG signals in Alzheimer's and Parkinson's disease (Accardo et al., 1997; Averna et al., 2023; Fiorenzato et al., 2024; Smits et al., 2016).

The 5-CSRTT has been widely used to understand the functional diversity of different sub-regions of the PFC in relation to attention and impulsive behavior (Dalley et al., 2008; Robbins, 2002). Adult rats with induced deafness showed deficits in initial learning of the 5-CSRTT as evidenced by an increased number of training days during the first session. However, as the training progressed, the groups did not differ in

the number of training days required. These results are consistent with our previous finding that adult rats with neomycin-induced deafening showed initial learning deficits in the 4-arm baited 8-arm radial maze task (Johne et al., 2022). Interestingly, it has been shown more recently that rats with noise-induced hearing impairment have difficulties to learn the initial rule of spatial maze tasks (Wieczerzak et al., 2021). Moreover, it has been shown that rats with lesions of the Cg1 subregion of the mPFC have a profound but transient attentional impairment in the early stages of behavioral testing (Wu et al., 2017), which is of interest in the context of our current finding that after deafening altered oscillatory activity is most pronounced in the Cg1. However, one recent study showed that about one week after noise-induced hearing loss electrophysiological recordings in awake free moving rats showed that spontaneous oscillations in the PFC is not affected. Nevertheless, authors already discussed that altered activity could manifest in the PFC at later time points (Wieczerzak et al., 2021). A limitation of this study is that because we used a single shank 32-electrode probe, which is optimal for resolving oscillatory activity of LFPs, it was not possible to analyze single-unit activity as we did in our previous study using high-impedance electrodes.

In addition, during training deafened rats made more incorrect responses in a non-stimulus hole as a measure of attention in the 5-CSRTT, whereas no group differences were found for premature responses, a marker for impulsivity. The dorsal Cg1 subregion of the mPFC is implicated in attentional aspects of performance (Fisher et al., 2020) as focal lesions of anterior Cg1 impair visual discriminative accuracy but have little effect on impulsivity (Chudasama et al., 2003; Passetti et al., 2002). In contrast, lesions of the PL and IL subregions of the mPFC have been shown to enhance premature responding as a measure of impulsivity, but they have no effect on accuracy (reviewed in Fisher et al., 2020). Together, these findings would support our hypothesis that altered oscillatory neuronal activity in the Cg1 subregion contributes to the impaired accuracy after deafening, whereas measures of impulsivity attributed to the ventral PL subregion of the PFC were almost not affected.

Neurons of the rodent PFC receive input from the auditory cortex and other regions, such as thalamus, hippocampus, and basal forebrain, allowing them to encode high-order information about sounds such as context, predictability, and valence (Hockley & Malmierca, 2024). The changes of neural activity found in the mPFC after deafening may involve altered temporal processing which probably result from altered inhibitory and excitatory properties of neurons including the predominant class of cortical GABAergic interneurons known as PV⁺ neurons (Caspary et al., 2008). PV⁺ neurons control the timing of pyramidal cell output in cortical neuron networks and are thus involved in cognitive function. In psychiatric disorders they have been shown to contribute to the disturbances of oscillatory network synchrony thought to underlie cognitive deficits (Gonzalez-Burgos et al., 2015). With the immunohistochemical methods used in the present study, however, no effect of hearing loss in adult rats on NeuN and PV expression within the prefrontal cortex could be found.

In the open field, deafened rats covered more distance, indicating a state of hyperlocomotion throughout the six months of testing. This finding was already indicated in our previous study, when adult deafened rats showed transient increased locomotor activity a few weeks after deafening (Johne et al., 2022). Interestingly, we reported more recently that juvenile deafened rats show hyperactivity throughout a six months testing period (Jelinek et al., 2024). However, in humans, hyperactivity has only been described in pediatric patients with hearing loss (González et al., 2021), whereas impaired motor activity in adults has not been reported.

Both the present and the previous group of adult deafened rats (Johne et al., 2022) showed reduced performance on the Rotarod, indicating impaired motor coordination, possibly due to Neomycin overspill into the vestibular organ. However, while the control rats spend more and more time on the Rotarod during the first few weeks of

testing, the rats in the deafened groups never spent more time on the Rotarod than on the first day. This finding may therefore indicate that the impaired motor coordination might be due to disturbed motor learning (Johne et al., 2022). Notably, rats deafened at juvenile age showed hyperactivity but showed no balance disturbances on the Rotarod during the whole test period, i.e., juvenile rats readily compensated possible balance deficits (Jelinek et al., 2024). Important, despite somewhat compromised motor balance and hyperactive behavior, the groups did not differ in the latency to nose poke after light signal, indicating that the compromised motor activity seen in the open field and Rotarod did not affect the ability to perform in the 5-CSRTT.

Similar to our previous study (Johne et al., 2022), deafened rats interacted less than non-operated controls. This differs from findings in juvenile deafened rats, where social play-fighting was even enhanced compared to control groups for almost the whole testing of six months (Jelinek et al., 2024). Interestingly, neither the controls nor the adult deafened rats in the present study showed play fighting, although juvenile-deafened rats never ceased to show play-fighting during the six months testing period (Jelinek et al., 2024). The review by Podury et al. (2023) pointed out that hearing loss may contribute to adverse psychosocial outcomes in the early life of humans (e.g., social isolation, depression). Infants with hearing impairment, often exhibit delayed language development and communication skills (Purves et al., 2001). However, adult-deafened rats in our study vocalized less with USV when social interaction was reduced at week 4, whereas later at week 16, no difference between groups in USV per social interaction was found. The observed normalization and reduced difference in USV between deafened rats and the non-operated group 16 weeks after surgery suggests recovery of social behavior along with vocalization after hearing loss in adult rats.

Our results indicate mild deficits in initial learning and attentional accuracy in deafened rats, which may be attributed to disturbed neural oscillations in the Cg1 subregion of the mPFC. This region receives input from the auditory cortex and other regions such as thalamus, hippocampus, and basal forebrain, which, together, allows encoding of high-order information about sounds. This integration of mPFC networks enables them to process complex auditory information and shape hearing perception and behavioral responses. Further investigation is warranted to explore the relationship between behavioral manifestations and neural correlates in the context of hearing loss, shedding light on the adaptive responses to hearing loss in the central auditory system.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Mariele Stenzel: Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Visualization, Conceptualization. **Mesbah Alam:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Marla Witte:** Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Jonas Jelinek:** Methodology. **Nina Armbrrecht:** Methodology, Investigation. **Adrian Armstrong:** Methodology, Formal analysis. **Andrej Kral:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Conceptualization. **Joachim K. Krauss:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Conceptualization. **Rüdiger Land:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Methodology, Investigation. **Kerstin Schwabe:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Marie Johne:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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